

Integrating Machine Learning models into the Linux Kernel: Opportunities and Challenges

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Abstract

The advent of the next generation of communication networks demands deep changes within current infrastructures. In this regard, the softwarization of the network following the Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) paradigms will be crucial to permit flexibility and programmability levels never seen before. This paper studies the opportunities that both the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies bring to this field. Their convergence enables the integration of intelligent ML-powered programs into the Linux kernel hence permitting almost every device in the network to perform a plethora of tasks, e.g., traffic processing, security analysis, etc. However, this integration is not straight-forward and poses a series of challenges that are discussed and solved in this work. To this end, a methodology for integrating complex ML models within the Linux kernel is proposed introducing specific tools in its different phases. This integration paves the way for the development of diverse virtual network functions in commodity hardware in an efficient and secure way.

Keywords: eBPF, Machine Learning, Linux, Kernel

1 Introduction

The emergence of 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) networks has brought a series of challenges and stringent requirements that network infrastructures need to cope with. Software Defined Networks (SDNs) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) paradigms has raised as the foundations for the construction of this kind of network architectures, enhancing their flexibility and robustness. Making use of these technologies, multiple solutions have been presented by the community during the last years to manage and orchestrate B5G infrastructures in an efficient way [8]. Besides, the changeover to this kind of systems demands a substantive investment in new software and infrastructure.

In this way, the softwarization of the network will be the cornerstone for providing flexibility to the new generation of communication systems. Furthermore, due to the increasing complexity in the different segments of these infrastructures, the introduction of intelligent techniques and mechanisms is of utmost importance to manage and orchestrate the unbundled B5G architecture. In this sense, the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) has surfaced as a promising solution to provide network flexibility and programmability in a simple and efficient way. It allows fast packet processing at kernel level, hence enabling the handling of incoming packets in the network interface in commodity hardware. This is because eBPF permits the safe execution of code inside the Linux kernel, which makes possible the use of non-specialized equipment in networking tasks. When combined with Machine Learning (ML), eBPF empowers intelligent and flexible networking at any point of the B5G infrastructure, which will help to address the challenges and requirements of the new generation of communication infrastructures.

These technologies are also handy to address security in B5G scenarios. Due to their characteristics, they are capable of perform real-time fast packet inspection to detect cyber threats. This is crucial in upcoming complex infrastructures, as the arrival of new paradigms and technologies bring together a plethora of new and unknown attack vectors. It is well-known that ML performs very well in cyberattacks detection, predict network behaviour or anticipate failures [3], therefore these virtual functions can be used to introduce network automation and self-healing processes without human supervision. In this way, this paper provides a detailed overview regarding the integration of ML-based processing into the Linux kernel. This milestone will bring freshness to different fields, e.g., device monitoring, data traffic management, cyber-security, etc. Therefore, the main contribution of this work is the presentation of a methodology for the implementation of complex ML models within the Linux kernel by leveraging the capabilities of eBPF. The proposal considers the usage of specific state-of-the-art tools for each stage of the methodology, placing a fundamental pillar for the design and development of intelligent virtual network modules, among other functionalities, in an efficient and simple way.

The rest of the document is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of existing proposals that combine eBPF and ML algorithms. Section 3 presents the opportunities that the usage of eBPF in next generation networks can bring, as well as its limitations. Section 4 details the proposed methodology and the tools that can be used. Finally, Section 5 concludes the document and proposes future research lines.

2 Background

eBPF permits the execution of isolated software artifacts in a privileged context within the Linux kernel. This feature enables the extension of the capabilities of the kernel while avoiding changes in the source code or losing efficiency. eBPF solutions can be used for a wide variety of use cases, but they are mainly employed for security, observability, and networking [18]. When interacting with the network, eBPF is frequently combined with the Linux eXpress Data Path (XDP), which permits the creation of flexible and powerful virtual network functions.

As aforementioned, the integration of ML in network management and orchestration will help to address the stringent demands of the next generation of communication networks. In the last years, as eBPF is standing out among other solutions due to its portability and flexibility, its use is being proposed in combination with ML algorithms to create intelligent and lightweight network functions. Typically, these solutions use (i) eBPF in the data plane to monitor traffic, enforce policies or rewrite packets at the lowest level, and (ii) ML algorithms in the control plane to analyze the data and take decisions in the application layer. For example, in [4], eBPF was used to monitor system calls and characterize the runtime behaviours of multiple microservices. With these data, authors managed to fingerprint these microservices based on how they used the system calls by feeding the data to a ML framework combining Bayesian learning and LSTM autoencoders. It was demonstrated that the proposed system can fingerprint microservices with a 99% accuracy. Another work in this line is the one developed in [23], in which an eBPF program extracted Linux system network data that was later trained with a LSTM model. With these data, the Linux network situation can be predicted through simulation, obtaining more accuracy in network security predictions than other similar methods. Authors in [22] used eBPF to monitor the operating system and identify different Redis working scenarios. With this information, an automatic tuning model based on random forest was used to maximize the performance of Redis by changing a set of parameter values. By doing so, the developed solution was able optimize the system at hardware level, achieving a higher performance than at application level.

As shown in the existing work, the combination of eBPF and ML is a powerful tool to enable flexible and lightweight monitoring and networking functions within the Linux kernel. However, all the aforementioned works decouple the monitoring or enforcing part from the intelligent one. That is, the eBPF program running at kernel level is used to monitor or to perform network actions, and the ML models and algorithms are executed in user space, fed by the data gathered by the eBPF program. In consequence, to the best of our knowledge, there is still no proposal that leverages the advantages of eBPF to integrate ML-powered processing at kernel level to boost the overall performance of the solutions.

3 eBPF: Opportunities and Challenges

3.1 eBPF evolution

Berkeley Packet Filter (BPF) was developed in 1992 as a kernel-level packet filtering solution for Unix BSD systems [12]. It included a virtual machine (VM) and a set of instructions for running programs written in the BPF language. The bytecode of the program was transmitted from user space to the kernel, where it underwent security checks before being associated with a socket and executed for incoming packets. The ability to allow secure execution of user-provided programs within the kernel led to the recognition of its potential applications beyond packet filtering, prompting the community to explore its kernel instrumentation capabilities in other domains. This paves the way for the development of *extended Berkeley Packet Filter* (eBPF), an enhanced version of BPF introduced in version 3.15 of the Linux kernel, which transformed BPF into a versatile in-kernel virtual machine.

Several significant modifications were made to BPF [9]. For example, eBPF introduced dynamic loading and program reloading capabilities within the virtual machine, enabling runtime modifications or reloading of programs as required. This feature enhanced the flexibility and adaptability of eBPF-based solutions, empowering users to modify program behavior without interrupting the system's operation. In addition, eBPF increased the number of registers from 2 to 11 (with 10 write registers), expanded register width from 32 bits to 64 bits, transitioned to a 64-bit instruction set, and added a 512-byte stack within the new engine. Another notable addition in eBPF is the introduction of maps, which are global data stores that enable persistent data storage between program executions and with the user space [16]. A good overview of how maps are used and defined in eBPF is given in [18]. Moreover, eBPF incorporated helper functions and system calls [15] that empowered developers to invoke kernel-level functions [10]. These tools provide the ability to interact with the kernel and perform a wide range of operations, such as manipulating network packets, performing packet filtering, or implementing custom routing logic.

3.2 Advantages and Applications

Considering the characteristics of eBPF, it arises as an adequate environment to run network functions that need to handle large amounts of traffic with low latency demands. This is due to the chance of avoiding packet-related data structure allocation when the packet arrives at the interface, which allows doing actions directly on the raw packet, hence saving time. Besides, the ability to compile and inject eBPF programs in the kernel at runtime enables many opportunities to deal with unexpected events in the network. In this way, when the network status changes, the code of the network function can be modified, adapting it to new needs, and dynamically put it into production without service interruptions. In addition to

these inherent eBPF advantages, the integration of ML models in these programs paves the way for the development of complex and intelligent VNF-based network management systems. Among the potential services and applications enabled by the convergence of these technologies, we highlight the following:

- **Routing management:** The advanced functionality provided by eBPF together with ML algorithms permits improving the performance of widely-used routing protocols. Authors of [21] focused on the Border Gateway Protocol (BGP) and presented a virtual machine based on eBPF for launching plugins that improve the performance of this routing protocol at runtime. Furthermore, different proposals have been oriented to improve the programmability of Linux's data plane by developing eBPF programs using the P4 language [5].
- **QoS:** The analysis of packet headers by the application of intelligent algorithms can improve the QoS provided to certain classes of traffic. For example, according to a set of rules, a prioritization of traffic flows can be performed at key points of the network infrastructure. Besides, packets can be tagged or labeled according to the information contained in their headers, e.g., source/destination address, type of application, DSCP field, etc. Another approach was proposed in [7], where an eBPF solution was integrated within the Linux TCP stack, permitting changing the established path by a TCP connection. This permits setting a new path to solve network interruptions or to make decisions related to QoS assurance.
- **Data plane supervision:** Two relevant eBPF applications are network function control and traffic monitoring. Considering the first one, it can be focused on measuring the latency introduced by network functions in charge of processing traffic flows [17]. This work proposed a monitoring module for measuring VNF's packet processing time. With this solution, it can be analyzed the impact of a single VNF or a chain of them. In turn, eBPF-based traffic monitoring is another relevant service, considering the massive traffic that eBPF programs can process employing limited computational resources [6]. Considering both applications, the integration of ML-based processing enables an intelligent decision-making process that may take advantage of all the data gathered by eBPF programs.
- **Firewall:** Thanks to the prominent performance of eBPF programs for inspecting traffic flows, they are excellent tools for improving the traditional Linux packet filtering mechanisms, especially considering the potential intelligence introduced by complex ML models. This enables efficient firewall functions such as network access control or Denial of Service (DOS) attack protection [2]. Besides, eBPF has been also leveraged to preserve user privacy for DNS-related queries [13]. The authors proposed a mechanism that permits to control of the DNS network traffic and ensures users' privacy with very low overhead and without modifications on the application level.
- **Security:** This broad field of study can be addressed from different perspectives, given the flexibility of eBPF programs and the opportunities brought by ML-based processing. Authors of [20] presented an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) implemented in eBPF. A traffic inspector is executed in kernel space and decides whether a packet should be forwarded to the user space to be analyzed by the IDS, thus limiting its computational load. Moreover, specialized ML models enable the implementation of security functions such as anomaly or intrusion detection [1, 19]. Considering the latter, the authors integrated a decision tree model within an eBPF program for detecting intrusions by the analysis of

key fields in different packet headers. From another perspective, work in [19] proposed an eBPF-based traffic collector for a given encrypted black-box service. These data are subsequently sent to an anomaly detection system based on a complex ML algorithm (random forest) which looks for abnormal behaviors or patterns.

3.3 eBPF Limitations

Programs developed in eBPF run in the kernel space, so they need to follow strict rules to protect the kernel. First, to ensure that each program runs and finishes fast, the number of instructions is limited to 4096 in the first kernel versions implementing eBPF and to 1 million in the newer ones (kernel 5.1 and above). Also, only bounded loops are allowed. Regarding the former, this is a challenge for developing network functions with some complexity. However, eBPF allows jumping from one program to another by means of “tail calls”, up to a maximum of 32 nested jumps. With this strategy, it can be avoided the limitation of the program length without suffering a very high overhead when jumping from one to another. Regarding the restrictions affecting loops, it directly impacts network functions that perform searches over a list of dynamic entries (for example, IP/MAC addresses tables) or parse flexible packet structures, for example, packet headers with a variable number of fields. Since the in-kernel verifier does not permit unbounded loops, the workaround consists of bounding the iterative structure with an upper limit and unrolling it at compile time. This is not a perfect solution as it produces longer programs and a notable loss of generality as the loop is limited at compile time. Another eBPF limitation consists of its inability to work with floating-point variables and operations. This is a significant drawback when working with complex ML models, e.g., neural networks, as their parameters (weights and biases in this case) are usually fractional numbers.

Additionally, the execution of eBPF programs is event-driven, in other words, eBPF programs attached to a network interface only are launched when a packet arrives. Therefore, the eBPF network functions are not always active, which makes it hard to handle timers or other events. Moreover, since the packets are processed before being allocated to kernel data structures, it is not easy to perform typical actions related to network protocols, such as retaining a packet for a certain time. Lastly, because of this event-driven and stateless nature, each processed packet can only receive one action, which prevents forwarding a given packet to several ports or interfaces at once. This issue can be fixed by moving the packets to deeper processing points inside the kernel or even to user space. However, this extra processing adds more delay which makes these solutions unsuitable for scenarios with severe latency constraints.

4 Proposed Methodology

In this section, we propose a general and structured methodology for developing programs containing ML-based processing devoted to running in the eBPF environment. As discussed above, integrating ML models into the eBPF kernel can provide significant benefits, but it is challenging due to the inherent limitations of eBPF. As a result, the traditional approach to deal with these technologies has been using eBPF to efficiently collect network data and then process these data using ML techniques in user space [11]. However, while this approach allows ML to be applied to network data, it does not fully exploit the strengths of eBPF, such as the efficient execution of code within the privileged context of the kernel, where it enjoys greater control and execution speed.

To achieve the integration of fully in-kernel ML models, our proposal focuses on the use of Python libraries to carry out the different stages of the training procedure, including hy-

perparameter optimization and the evaluation of accuracy metrics. Among these libraries, the following options stand out:

- **Scikit-Learn:** It is one of the most popular and widely used ML libraries in Python. It is designed to be simple and efficient, focusing primarily on supervised and unsupervised learning algorithms. Scikit-Learn provides tools for classification, regression, clustering, feature selection, data preprocessing, and model evaluation. It is an excellent choice for those new to ML due to its ease of use and extensive documentation.
- **TensorFlow:** It is a flexible, open-source library created by Google for deep learning and ML. It can construct complex neural networks, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). Due to its numerous features, TensorFlow is extensively utilized in both research and production within the deep learning field, and it boasts a sizeable community of tool developers. TensorFlow also offers TensorFlow.js for web applications and TensorFlow Lite for mobile devices.
- **PyTorch:** It is another open-source ML library, primarily developed by Facebook and its AI research team. It has become extremely popular in the deep learning community due to its flexibility and dynamic model-building capabilities. PyTorch is known for its “autograd” feature, which allows developers to define and modify models more intuitively. This makes it particularly useful for deep learning research and experimenting with complex models. PyTorch also has a large user community and is increasingly being adopted by the industry.

As detailed previously, at this point it is important to be aware of the limitations of the Linux kernel on the use of floating-point operations. Therefore, it is advisable to avoid ML models, activation functions, etc. that involve floating-point operations and, in cases where they are necessary during the training process, efforts should be made to optimize and possibly bypass them during inference in the eBPF implementation.

Our proposed next step is to use libraries and tools that facilitate the implementation of ML algorithms on resource-constrained environments such as those in the context of TinyML [14]. In particular, some frameworks convert trained models from the ML libraries mentioned above into formats suitable for execution on resource-constrained platforms. By leveraging the simplicity of the generated code, it can be more easily integrated in eBPF programs. The following frameworks and libraries are good examples of TinyML solutions:

- **TensorFlow Lite:** It is a widely used TinyML library developed by Google. It provides a comprehensive set of tools for adapting TensorFlow models to run efficiently on mobile and embedded devices. The library consists of two main components: The converter and the interpreter. The converter is responsible for transforming TensorFlow models into optimized code that can run on resource-constrained platforms. On the other hand, the interpreter is responsible for executing the code generated by the converter. TensorFlow Lite supports a wide variety of optimized models, including those based on neural networks, and enables their execution on platforms such as smartphones, embedded Linux systems, and Micro Controller Units (MCUs). This versatility allows efficient ML algorithms to be deployed on a wide range of devices in the TinyML ecosystem.
- **ELL:** Microsoft has also made its contribution to TinyML with the release of the Embedded Learning Library (ELL), an open-source framework that enables the design and deployment of pre-trained ML models on resource-constrained platforms such as Arduino, Raspberry Pi, and micro:bit.

- **MicroML**: Although several TinyML frameworks focus primarily on neural networks, there are other initiatives that extend their support to other ML techniques, including the Naive Bayes classifier, decision trees, and k-nearest Neighbours (k-NN), among others. MicroML is a project that facilitates the adaptation of Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Relevance Vector Machine (RVM) algorithms to C code, ensuring compatibility with various microcontrollers such as Arduino, ESP8266, and ESP32.
- **emlearn**: It is another framework that plays a crucial role in the TinyML landscape by providing the means to generate ML models in portable C99 code. This code is derived from popular Python libraries such as Scikit-learn and Keras. The emlearn framework supports a wide range of ML algorithms, including Random Forest (RF), Decision Trees, Naive Bayes, and Linear Models.

Once a TinyML library has allowed us to get the trained ML model in a simple and portable code, the next step is inspect this code to overcome the limitations of eBPF's in-kernel programs. For the unbounded loops, as explained above, the proposal is to modify them so that the number of iterations is known at compile time and they can be loaded into the kernel unrolled. As for floating-point operations, if there is no way to avoid them, our suggestion is to develop a fixed-point representation that uses 32-bit integers to represent floating-point values, using one bit for the sign, some bits for the integer part, and the rest for the fractional part, adapting the arithmetic functions accordingly. Note that 64-bit integers are required for multiplication to maintain precision. Finally, to collect data from the network, the ML algorithm must be combined with a packet parsing process to obtain information about the packets arriving at the network interface, and eBPF maps can store information between eBPF executions.

Table 1 sums up the proposed methodology, which permits to obtain ML-enabled eBPF programs capable of running within the Linux kernel.

Table 1: Proposed methodology to integrate ML models into eBPF in-kernel programs

Step #	Description	Example Tools
1	Full ML model generation	Scikit-Learn TensorFlow PyTorch
2	ML model code simplification	TensorFlow lite ELL MicroML emlearn
3	Code adaptation to eBPF restrictions	Visual inspection Code debugging tools

5 Conclusion

This paper has studied the opportunities that both eBPF and ML bring to current and future network infrastructures. The convergence of these technologies enables the integration of intelligent algorithms based on ML into the Linux kernel, which ensures their fast and secure execution in commodity hardware. This is of special relevance in scenarios considering fog or

edge computing such as in the Internet of Things (IoT). Besides, the potential challenges related to the limitations of eBPF-based development have been identified and different solutions have been provided. Lastly, a general methodology for implementing complex ML models in eBPF programs that can run within the Linux kernel has been proposed. This is a first step towards the design and development of a wide range of network functions that may be instantiated in different types of devices, hence enriching the flexibility and scalability of network infrastructures. Next research steps are focused on the development of functional ML-powered eBPF-based implementations following the discussed precepts.

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